

Combating Online Gender-Based Violence: A Multi-Criteria Decision-Making Framework for Evaluating Information Security Solutions

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Abstract

Online gender-based violence is a major impediment to digital engagement and security, especially for women and gender minorities. The prevalence of cyber harassment, doxing, nonconsensual image sharing, and online stalking highlights the critical need for specific, gender-sensitive information security measures. The Preference ranking organization method for enrichment evaluation (PROMETHEE-II), a multi-criteria decision-making method, is used in this study to create a structured decision-support framework for evaluating and ranking possible online gender-based violence options. In order to ensure safety, accessibility, and usability for victims and at-risk users, five practical and extensively discussed alternatives are chosen for evaluation: end-to-end encryption tools, AI-based content moderation systems, anonymous reporting platforms, digital literacy and cyber hygiene training programs, as well as emergency support applications. These alternatives are evaluated based on five factors: effectiveness, ease of use, anonymity, cost, and speed of response. The study compares solutions and produces a comprehensive rating using PROMETHEE-II, which applies preference functions and stakeholder-defined weights. The findings show that digital literacy initiatives and emergency support apps had the best net flow scores, demonstrating their greater capacity to strike a balance between user privacy, efficacy, and cost. Policymakers, technologists, and digital rights advocates can use this research's quantitative and replicable methodology to assess gender-sensitive cybersecurity strategies and to prioritize and choose interventions that reduce online gender-based violence and promote inclusive digital safety.

Keywords: Online Gender-Based Violence (OGBV), Multi-Criteria Decision Making (MCDM), Information Security, PROMETHEE-II, Gender Equity

INTRODUCTION

Communication and connectedness have been profoundly altered by the digital age, but it has also brought about new kinds of harm, especially for women and girls. Online Gender-Based Violence (OGBV), which includes systematic abuse, doxing, harassment, cyberstalking, and non-consensual image sharing, has become a serious worldwide problem (Almenar, 2021; Ostadtaghizadeh et al., 2023). United Nations and World Health Organization report that one in three women has been the victim of internet abuse, which disproportionately affects underprivileged groups (UN, 2024; WHO, 2024). In addition to endangering psychological and emotional health, these violations prevent people from fully engaging in social life, education, and digital environments (Bansal et al., 2024; Dunn, 2020).

While information security is conventionally defined by its commitment to protecting the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of digital systems, its vital role in the prevention

of Online Gender-Based Violence (OGBV) remains significantly under-researched. Tools like secure authentication, content filtering, and end-to-end encryption guard against common online threats, but they frequently lack the gender-sensitive design required to address social ills (Hofstetter & Pourmalek, 2023). Recent multidisciplinary studies have highlighted the necessity for feminist and people-centred cybersecurity strategies that put an emphasis on contextual privacy, user autonomy, and inclusive design (Bansal et al., 2024). Meuller (2023) asserts that a feminist cybersecurity framework provides a revolutionary alternative to conventional, state-focused models for combating online extremism. This paradigm shift emphasizes human security, inclusivity, and care-oriented interventions. By prioritizing the experiences of marginalized victims, the framework aims to dismantle the systemic power disparities that perpetuate extremism, thereby redefining cybersecurity as the advancement of digital safety and equity. Gurumurthy and Chami (2017) advocate a feminist framework that connects gender, technology, and development, highlighting women's rights to access, knowledge, and advancement in the digital era. They argue that true digital inclusion requires structural reforms in governance and knowledge systems, moving beyond neoliberal models to promote equity, justice, and women's empowerment in the information society. Nevertheless, there are still numerous disjointed interventions and few frameworks for methodically evaluating their cost, inclusivity, effectiveness, and usability.

The body of existing literature covers a variety of societal and technical reactions to OGBV (Santos & Pourmalek, 2022). Infrastructure protection is provided by technological solutions like encryption and AI-based content monitoring, but they face challenges like algorithmic bias and accessibility (Pasipamire, 2024). For victims, emergency assistance applications and anonymous reporting platforms offer reactive mechanisms, while digital literacy initiatives work to foster proactive, self-protective behaviours. The necessity of comprehensive assessment methods that take into account the practical compromises victims may make when choosing or depending on these technologies has been emphasized by academics (Al-Alosi, 2020; Barter & Koulu, 2021).

Current approaches to OGBV include community reporting, cybercrime laws, digital literacy campaigns, and content moderation with secure messaging (Jahan Antara et al., 2025; Setyaningsih et al., 2024). Systematic frameworks for assessing these solutions according to several, frequently incompatible criteria, including usability, affordability, privacy, and effectiveness, are still lacking, nevertheless. Methods of multi-criteria decision-making (MCDM) provide an organized approach to assist with this assessment (Sahoo & Goswami, 2023). Using preference functions and pairwise comparisons, Preference Ranking Organization Method for Enrichment Evaluation (PROMETHEE-II) in particular, enables a comprehensive ranking of alternatives (Goswami, 2020). Although it has been used in fields like cybersecurity policy (Torbacki, 2021), urban planning (Babaei et al., 2018), and environmental sustainability (Wątróbski, 2023), its application to gender-sensitive information security is yet relatively unexplored.

Despite the growing awareness of OGBV and the rise of technology-driven solutions, limited research integrates gender analysis, cybersecurity frameworks, and MCDM methodologies into a cohesive decision-support model. This study fills that gap by identifying and evaluating five key OGBV interventions from a gendered InfoSec perspective. It then applies the PROMETHEE-II method to rank these interventions using five relevant criteria: effectiveness, ease of use, anonymity, cost, and response speed. The main advantage of the PROMETHEE-II ranking method is that it provides a clear and complete order of all options. This helps decision-makers easily compare alternatives and choose the most appropriate OGBV solution for victims or those at risk. Furthermore, the research provides a replicable model for stakeholders to adapt in diverse policy and design contexts. By connecting the technical and social aspects of cybersecurity, the study helps build a digital safety system that is both fairer and more effective.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

PROMETHEE-II is used in this study to rank and assess online solutions that combat gender-based violence. By computing net preference flows that account for each alternative's benefits and drawbacks in relation to the others, PROMETHEE-II allows for the systematic comparison of options when several, frequently incompatible criteria are present (Isa et al., 2021).

Selection of Alternatives

The evaluation of contemporary digital safety and gender-based violence mitigation methods and technologies led to the identification of five workable and feasible solutions:

- i. End-to-end encryption (E2EE): This technology guarantees safe connection while shielding user data from unwanted access and leakage (Blaise et al., 2021).
- ii. AI-Based Content Moderation: This method identifies and eliminates offensive gender-based content from the internet by using machine learning (Ahmed & Khan, 2024).
- iii. Anonymous Reporting Platforms: These let users report events without disclosing who they are (Messman et al., 2024).
- iv. Digital Literacy and Cyber Hygiene Training: This equips users with the knowledge to identify, steer clear of, and report online abuse (Kostiantyn, 2025).
- v. Emergency Support Apps: These are smartphone apps that provide one-tap notifications and direct connections to support groups or emergency services (Srinivasan & Dharani, 2025).

These were selected due to their applicability, accessibility, and representation of technical and instructional strategies for OGBV response and prevention.

Evaluation Criteria

Five evaluation criteria were created through literature study and expert consultation, focusing on practical issues in online safety interventions:

- i. Effectiveness (C1): The extent to which the solution stops or lessens gender-based violence on the internet.
- ii. Ease of Use (C2): User-friendliness and accessibility, especially for non-technical users.
- iii. Anonymity (C3): The degree to which the user's identity is protected by the solution.
- iv. Cost (C4): Cost-effectiveness and simplicity of use.
- v. Speed of Response (C5): The rate at which the solution recognizes, stops, or responds to threats.

Each criterion was assigned a weight reflecting its perceived importance, as shown in Table 1:

Table 1. Criterion Weights

Criterion	Weight
Effectiveness	0.25
Ease of Use	0.20
Anonymity	0.25
Cost	0.10
Response Speed	0.20

Alternatives were scored on a 1–5 scale for each criterion based on existing literature, case studies, and expert insights. These raw scores were then normalized using min-max normalization to ensure comparability across criteria.

PROMETHEE-II Procedure

Step 1: Standardize the decision matrix (evaluation matrix) using the formulas from equations 1 and 2.

$$\text{Beneficial Criteria: } R_{ij} = \frac{[x_{ij} - (x_{ij})]}{[(x_{ij}) - (x_{ij})]} \quad (1)$$

$(i = 1, 2, \dots, m; j = 1, 2, \dots, n)$

$$\text{Non-beneficial Criteria: } R_{ij} = \frac{[(x_{ij}) - x_{ij}]}{[(x_{ij}) - (x_{ij})]} \quad (2)$$

where x_{ij} is the value of each criterion, (x_{ij}) is the minimum score for each criterion, and x_{ij} is the maximum score for each criterion.

Step 2: Calculate the evaluation differences between the i^{th} choice and the other alternatives using equation 3.

$$D = R_{aj} - R_{bj} \quad (3)$$

where R_{aj} is the normalized score of a criterion, a, and R_{bj} is the normalized value of a criterion, b.

Step 3: Utilizing equation 4, compute the preference function, $P_j(a, b)$.

$$P_j(a, b) = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } R_{aj} \leq R_{bj} \\ R_{bj} D, & \text{otherwise } R_{aj} > R_{bj} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

Step 4: As stated in equation 5, construct a function $\pi(a, b)$ that aggregates preferences.

$$\pi(a, b) = \frac{[\sum_{j=1}^n w_j P_j(a, b)]}{\sum_{j=1}^n w_j} \quad (5)$$

where w_j represents the weights displayed in Table 1.

Step 5: Compute the leaving (positive) outranking flow and the entering (negative) outranking flow, φ^+ and φ^- respectively. They are stated in equations 6 and 7.

$$\varphi^+ = \frac{1}{m-1} \sum_{b=1}^m \pi(a, b) \quad (a \neq b) \quad (6)$$

$$\varphi^- = \frac{1}{m-1} \sum_{b=1}^m \pi(b, a) \quad (a \neq b) \quad (7)$$

where m represents the number of options.

Step 6: Determine the net outranking flow for every alternative as expressed in equation 8.

$$\varphi(a) = \varphi^+(a) - \varphi^-(a) \quad (8)$$

Step 7: Decide which alternatives should be considered first, based on the values of $\varphi(a)$.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Alternatives were scored on a 1–5 scale for each criterion based on hybrid approach of consultations with two cybersecurity researchers, one gender-right advocate, and two OGBV survivors as shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Decision Matrix

Alternatives/ Criteria	Effectiveness	Ease of use	Anonymity	Cost	Response Speed
E2EE	4	3	3	3	4
AI Content Moderation	3	4	5	4	3
Anonymous Reporting	4	4	5	5	2
Digital Literacy	5	5	3	3	3
Emergency Support	4	4	3	3	5

Using the PROMETHEE-II method, five chosen solutions to online gender-based violence were ranked in order of performance across five weighted criteria. As indicated in Table 3, the entering flow, leaving flow, and net preference flow (ϕ) values offer a numerical foundation for evaluating the relative merits of each option.

Table 3. PROMETHEE-II Ranking of OGBV Solutions

	Leaving Flow	Entering Flow	Net Preference Flow	Rank
E2EE	0.135416667	0.297916667	-0.1625	5
AI Content Moderation	0.241666667	0.26875	-0.027083333	4
Anonymous Reporting	0.24375	0.260416667	-0.016666667	3
Digital Literacy	0.335416667	0.175	0.160416667	1
Emergency Support	0.227083333	0.18125	0.045833333	2

The results provide key insights about how information security interventions might be used in practice to stop gender-based violence online. With the highest net flow, digital literacy had the best overall performance across all categories. On the other hand, end-to-end encryption scored the lowest, indicating that it is not as effective as the other solutions. Figure 1 shows a graphical illustration of the OGBV.

Figure 1. Graph of OGBV Solutions Ranking

Training in digital literacy is effective because it prevents attacks by educating users, particularly women and girls, about safe online behaviour. It is more affordable, scalable, and empowering than technical tools, although offering a slower reaction time.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The PROMETHEE-II multi-criteria decision-making process was used in this study to assess and rank five strategies for preventing gender-based violence online. The most promising solutions were found to be anonymous reporting platforms and digital literacy training, according to a systematic comparison based on five useful criteria: effectiveness, ease of use, anonymity, cost, and speed of response.

In order to lessen the negative effects of OGBV, the results indicate that preventive, anonymous, and user-empowering methods are more appealing and successful. This research enables well-informed data-driven decisions that meet the demands of diverse user communities and improve the responsiveness and inclusivity of digital safety programs by providing a framework that is both reproducible and flexible.

This model may be expanded in future studies by applying PROMETHEE-II in various sociocultural and geographic contexts, examining hybrid approaches, or integrating qualitative inputs.

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